

Table 1. Comparison of CH₄ emission between different rice cultivation methods and different irrigation systems.

Year	Site ^a	Cropping system	Fertilizer application (kg/ha)		CH ₄ emission flux (mg/m ² per h)		Reduction
			Organic	Inorganic	Conventional irrigation	Intermittent irrigation	
1990	BJI	Rice after wheat	Horse manure 15,000	NH ₄ HCO ₃ 610	35.9	14.6	59 ^b
1991	BJII	Spring rice	Pig manure 15,000	Urea 500	10.0	8.7	15 ^c
1990	NJI	Rice after wheat	Pig manure 15,000	Urea 188	10.8		
1992	BJIII	Spring rice	Pig manure 7,500	Urea 300	8.5	5.6	34
1990	NJII	Rice after wheat	Pig manure 45,000			9.5	12
					<i>Dry seeded</i>	<i>Conventional</i>	
1991	BJII	Spring rice	Pig manure 95,000	Urea 300	2.6	10.0	74
1992	BJIII	Spring rice	Pig manure 75,000	Urea 300	3.5	8.5	59
					<i>Ridge culture</i>	<i>Conventional</i>	
1990	NJI	Rice after wheat	Pig manure 15,000	Urea 188	6.6	10.8	39
1991	NJII	Rice after wheat	Pig manure 12,500	Urea 200	11.3	19.8	43
1991	NJII	Rice after wheat	Pig manure 25,000	Urea 200	13.7		31 ^d

^a BJ = Beijing, NJ = Nanjing. ^b Poor soil permeability. ^c Good soil permeability. ^d Organic fertilizer doubled.

Table 2. Comparison of CH₄ emission between different rice varieties. 1991.

Site ^a	Variety	Cropping system	Fertilizer application (kg/ha)		CH ₄ emission flux (mg/m ² per h)	Yield (t/ha)
			Organic	Inorganic		
NJI	Conventional	Rice after wheat	Pig manure 15,000	Urea 150	34.8	4.7
NJI	Hybrid	Rice after wheat	Pig manure 15,000	Urea 150	25.2	6.8

^a NJI = Nanjing.

b) Adjusting inorganic fertilizer application time: Data show that adjusting the application time of the different inorganic fertilizers may reduce CH₄ emission. Research at the Chinese Academy of Environmental Sciences revealed that CH₄ emission may be controlled if ammonium sulfate and urea application are reasonably delayed to cover the two emission peaks; more tests are needed to verify this observation.

Since 1985, China has maintained its rice area at 32 million ha. It is estimated that no remarkable increase in this area

will occur by the year 2000 and that it is possible to reduce CH₄ emission by about 20%. More studies are needed to confirm these methods.

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Effects of heat balance on methane emission in rice plant canopy

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Methane emission from agricultural wetlands, although a direct result of soil bacterial activity, should be a function of temperature, water regime, root exudates, organic residues, plant metabolism, and physicochemical and biological properties of soils (Conrad 1989). Diurnal fluctuation of CH₄ emission is strongly dependent on the temperature changes of the upper soil layer, with maximum CH₄ emission under high soil temperature (Shütz et al 1989).

Various micrometeorological elements related to the heat balance within the rice plant canopy and CH₄ emission rates were monitored at different growth stages in ricefields into which organic matter had been incorporated.

The experiment was conducted at Suwon Weather Station (37° 16' N, 126° 59' E, 39 m) in 1993. Twenty-day-old seedlings of the rice variety, Ilpoombyeo, was transplanted on 20 May. Fertilizers were applied at 110-30.8-66.4 kg NPK/ha along with 7.4 t rice straw/ha.

Micrometeorological elements measured within the rice plant canopy were hourly solar radiation, net radiation, soil heat flux, relative humidity, air temperature, water temperature (average over 4 cm depth), and soil temperature (at 5 cm depth). Heat balances within the rice canopy were determined by Bowen ratio method. Three types of chambers, with dimensions of 30 × 60 × 125 cm, 15 × 30 × 45 cm, and 30 × 60 × 85 cm, were used to measure CH₄ emission rates.

CH₄ emission rates from the rice canopy were highly correlated with water temperature, soil temperature, latent heat flux, and sensible heat flux (see table). This indicates that incoming energy flux and evapotranspiration from the plant canopy influenced CH₄ emission rates at the canopy level. CH₄ emission rates per unit leaf area showed

Correlation matrix between CH₄ emission rates and micrometeorological elements. Suwon, Korea, 1993.

Element	Air temperature	Relative humidity	Temperature		Radiation		Heat flux			
			Water	Soil	Total	Net	Soil	Latent	Sensible	
Canopy	Emission (E)	-0.05	-0.23	0.57**	0.67**	-0.08	-0.04	-0.39	0.70**	0.36
	E/LAI	-0.18	0.06	0.51*	0.60**	0.01	0.47	-0.77**	0.57*	0.56**
Water surface	Emission (E)	0.53*	-0.44	0.85**	0.77**	0.38	0.36	-0.74**	0.79**	0.81**
	E/LAI	0.20	-0.07	0.62**	0.63**	0.26	0.28	-0.87**	0.59**	0.74**

the highest correlation with soil heat flux ($r = 0.77^{**}$) compared with the other elements. This finding suggests that solar energy plays an important role as a thermal energy source for CH₄ emission, and that the amount of energy reaching the ground where methanogenic bacteria live may be more important than previously thought in determining CH₄ emission. (See the figure for temporal changes in daily means of water and ground temperatures along with CH₄ emission rates estimated as a function of these temperatures.)

We determined the estimation models by combining the respective estimation formulas developed under either bright or dark conditions. CH₄ emission were estimated by using one of two regression equations: $Y = -2347.12 + 221.5488x - 3.75347x^2$ as a function of water temperature or $Y = -3205.08 + 27.501x - 1.29756x^2$ as a function of ground temperature. During the early growing

season (from May to early June), CH₄ emission fluctuated greatly, depending strongly on the temporal variations in water and ground temperatures.

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Impact of gypsum application on methane emission from a wetland ricefield

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A frequently suggested option to mitigate CH₄ emission from ricefields is use of sulfate-containing fertilizers, such as (NH₄)₂SO₄, because sulfate reducers (in the presence of SO₄²⁻) can outcompete methanogens for substrates (Martens and Berner 1974, Lovley and Klug 1983). Methanogens may coexist with sulfate reducers, however, when there are zones or spots with low sulfate content (Martens and Berner 1974). CH₄ emission measurements in ricefields fertilized with (NH₄)₂SO₄ gave contradicting results, presumably because of variations in *in situ* SO₄²⁻ concentrations in the different field experiments.

To elucidate the impact of sulfate availability on CH₄ emission, field experiments with gypsum (CaSO₄) application were carried out during the 1991 and 1992 wet seasons (WS) (Jul-Nov) in a wetland ricefield at Los Baños, Philippines. CH₄ emission rates were monitored with an automatic measurement system based on the closed chamber technique described by Schutz et al (1989), with minor modifications. CH₄ emission rates were calculated with linear regression from the temporal increase of the CH₄ concentration in the chamber ($Y^2 > 0.95$). The SO₄²⁻ concentration in the soil solution was measured on a dionex ionchromatograph at the beginning and end of the 1991 growing season.

CH₄ emission from fields with green manure (GM) was strongly enhanced